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Abstract

Although Namibia is an independent and peaceful country with a progressive constitution, colonial hangovers and environmental patterns including drought, deforestation and floods are some factors that have trapped her in poverty (Kaereho et al., 2016). Climate change has been identified as one of the most daunting challenges of the twenty-first century, causing an increase in seawater levels, changes in global temperatures, and droughts and floods in many parts of the world. Moreover, in the early part of 2020, the world had the worse experience of the 21st century—an unimaginable and unpredictable pandemic. Before the outbreak of COVID-19, plans and practices were in place to explore the links between the economy and climate change, focusing on the economic crisis conveyed by climate change. However, they have inclined to be treated separately in policy and practice in many developing countries. But many of these plans were put on halt as the fight against pandemics became the priority. In addition, with the outbreak of COVID-19, many countries also witnessed the connection between climate change, COVID-19 and the economy, with special relevance to the community and environment. This paper is a qualitative explorative with the use of the grounded theory approach. The data was collected by the use of existing data that has been systematically collected and analysed. The study employed a thematic content analysis method.

Keywords: Climate change, COVID-19, Global pandemic, Economic crises, Social crises, Namibia, Southern Africa, Urbanisation, Poverty, Inequality

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Introduction

Numerous countries in Africa are still developing their economy but their demand to adapt to twenty-first-century technology is very high. In doing this, there are many challenges to be faced, such as technological advancement, global economic crises, poverty and inequality and climate change. In 2020, the public health measures of many countries were evaluated and challenged during the devastating global COVID-19 pandemic, which first reared its head in 2019, with much of its impact being realised and suffered in 2020. The novel 'Corona virus' or COVID-19 that spread around the globe in less than five months infected and killed millions of people worldwide. COVID-19 hastily transformed public health, revealing the vulnerabilities, inequalities and social crisis in many countries to an epic proportion.

Namibia is inclined to natural disasters, such as frequent flooding and drought events. The country experienced devastating droughts in recent years. However, a drought is a regular feature of Namibia, but it does not affect all parts of the country in any given year. The National Drought Policy & Strategy of Namibia was developed in 1997 to protect against the devastation of droughts. In addition to natural disasters, time and again, Namibia is stricken by diseases and virus outbreaks such as malaria, Hepatitis-E, smallpox, tuberculosis (TB), and HIV/AIDS, to name a few common. However, none of these diseases and infections have reached the capacity at which COVID-19 reshaped and impacted the Namibian society at large. COVID-19 transformed many industries in the country and halted many economic development plans. COVID-19 pandemic and climate change have presented physical destruction to economies, social function, global political and public health as a result of the shutting down of almost all economic activities and changing or creating policies as part of the effort to control the global issues.

Review of Literature

Impact of Climate Change on the Namibian Community and Economy

The world is changing and Namibia is trying hard to keep up with them. Food insecurity, drought, poverty, access to education and health, and water scarcity are but a few of the country's pre-existing inequality. This has led Namibia to develop new climate resilience plans or policies that allow it to become more self-sustainable and reduce its dependency on neighbouring countries such as South Africa. Rainy seasons vary in Namibia. The country may at times experience a short monsoon, and at other times, a much longer and more joyful raining season. Namibia is deeply dependent on natural resources and is ranked second in aridity after the Sahara Desert. Rainfall is extremely inconstant, and at times, predictable statistical indicators are not always accurate with annual rain reports. Thus, the mean and median are often difficult to use.

Climate change has put pressure on farming economies like communal and commercial agriculture (crop and livestock), food production and processing, and small mining sectors. In addition, Namibia has to now refocus and become more climate resistant in its development plans. Many of its communities are profoundly impacted by climate change in a variety of ways. From 2011 to 2018, the country experienced the most devastating drought that lasted for more than five years. While some parts of Namibia reported rainfall after 2015, the entire central-west regions, the far north-west regions, the central east regions and the southern region of the country received no rain or reported extremely poor rainfall for the entire drought period. The south-western parts of Namibia received winter rain from May to July, similar to the north-western Cape in South Africa. This rainfall accounted for more than half the annual total rainfall for the southern region, which benefited the farming system in the region, especially the grape productions found in this mostly dry topography.

Land usage in Namibia varies. There is farming (crop, livestock and game, commercial and subsistence, and small and large scale); conservation on proclaimed state-protected areas; resource use, management and conservation on registered communal conservancies; areas earmarked for resettlement; urban areas and informal settling; government agriculture farms; and tourism and mining (Ministry of Environment and Tourism, 2010).

End of the Hunting Season and Wild Food Gathering

Hunting has now become more of a seasonal activity, and many are doing it for sport or leisure. According to MacLaren et al. (2019), there are about six types of consumption of wildlife practices that are permitted in Namibia under varying conditions. The first is shoot-and-sell, the second is trophy hunting, the third is biltong hunting, the fourth is management hunting, the fifth is shooting for own use and finally the live capture and sale of wildlife. To take a step into the past of Namibia, San communities and many other indigenous groups of Namibia hunted wildlife for their meat and showed various ways to appreciate the food or meat from the animal they killed. The introduction of European settlers in Namibia and the war from 1904 to 1907 resulted in many Namibian groups losing their lives, land, cattle, livestock and homes. The Europeans started to build farmland that they owned and controlled, while the black community became labourers to the Europeans. Many were forced into reserve areas for black people. These areas were managed by a Police Zone that control the movement of the black community in Namibia. Most of the wild animals that were hunted by the indigenous groups found refuge in the European farms, as the African Reserves were over-populated, and there were large herds of cattle. Wildlife was perceived as more than a threat to crops, livestock and infrastructure, as well as community safety.

Consequently, indigenous groups like the San people, who depended and still depend totally on hunting and gathering, were forced to adhere to and obey the country's laws and regulations on hunting. Moreover, they were confronted with seasonal climate changes and the challenges of adapting to new ways of doing things versus what they had practised for generations. The extremely poor rainfall from 2011 to 2018 led to a much shorter season for hunting and a decrease in wildlife as a result of famine caused by drought. In recent years, wild berries and other foods that people gathered in the wild have yielded enough produce, resulting in more people depending on government subsidies. As a method of money-making, small groups of people in rural areas sold foods like wild berries locally known as eembe to people in cities or towns. This helped them earn a livelihood so they could buy food such as maize meals, sugar and other products they might need to sustain their large families. With the climate change, many of these people could not gather enough berries or other wild fruits to sell; this impacted their livelihood.

2019 Drought on the Namibian Economy

In 2019, another wave of drought hit the country, one that is now described as the worst of the last 90 years (Shikangalah, 2020). As a result, the annual agricultural output of Namibia fell to under 50 per cent of its previous output. Crop yield was reduced, and livestock production was already in decline due to poor rainfall in the earlier seasons. This led the 2019 drought to be declared a national disaster and a national drought emergency on 6 May 2019. A Drought Response Plan was established and implemented countrywide. The plan included food delivery for vulnerable communities and livestock marketing encouragements, such as LIS subsidies and bank loans. Government and commercial banks were pressurised in taking total responsibility assuring smooth assistance in delivering relevant services for the affected and the needy communities in this regard.

Namibia's rural communities that deeply depend on natural resources, such as land for agriculture, remain the poorest and are most vulnerable to the negative impacts of climate change (Ministry of Environment & Tourism, 2010). There were instances during the drought period when many people in rural areas had no food and water for days. This vulnerability was worsened by existing marginal or lack of adequate service delivery to isolated areas such as the Kaokoland, which are generally considered prohibitively expensive during difficult times. Coupled with low population densities, long travel distances and lack of infrastructure like adequate road networks, further increased the country's vulnerability to climate change. There is a need to mobilise and support these members of society so they can deal with climate change. Adaptive abilities among vulnerable groups who are indigenous to the land are considered to be very low, and this has caused them to face

numerous challenges. It should be realised and elucidated that many Namibian indigenous groups do not understand climate change, hence the term or concept of climate change does not exist in many native languages. This makes it hard to educate the groups on climate change. As a result, the recognition of climate change risks and opportunities is still equally new in Namibia.

The first policy on climate change in Namibia was developed in the late 1900s. The Constitution of Namibia highlights the need to develop and implement policies to maintain ecosystems, ecological processes and biological diversity for the benefit of the present and future generations. The predicted negative effects of climate change may compromise the ability of the state to fulfil its obligations. Namibia does not have an existing drought monitoring system to reduce the economic liability that droughts bring to the nation and, in particular, to its farming community and people in the rural areas of the country.

Impact of COVID-19 on Communities and the Economy

On 17 March 2020, Namibia declared COVID-19 as a state of emergency and responded with urgent measures to contain the further spread of the novel Coronavirus in the country. At that time, the country had reported only two cases, both of whom were foreigners. No local transmission was yet found. To combat the situation, certain measures were employed by the Namibian government. These are as follows:

- Travel to all countries of the world was banned and all the borders were closed
- All the returning Namibians and permanent residents were subjected to a mandatory 14-day quarantine
- All government, state-owned enterprise and private sector employees were to operate from home for 14 days
- All nightclubs, shebeens, bars and markets were closed for 14 days
- Travel in or out of the Khomas and Erongo region was restricted for 21 days

The government under the State of Emergency only gave permission for the operation of essential services and the sale of essential products. The movement of people conveying these essential services or goods was allowed.

These new restrictions and operation changes had taken Namibia by a storm, so much so that healthcare systems feared for their capacity, and many economic sectors were on the verge of collapsing. Schools and institutions of higher learning adopted online learning. An article by Amukeshe (2020) states

that economic activities in Namibia between April and June decreased by around N\$4 billion in comparison to 2019 in the same period, resulting 11.1 per cent decline. This had been the worst-ever recorded economic decline in the country. Experts around the country started questioning whether the lockdowns were worth the cost in an already challenged economy. Many people lost their jobs because the private sector was not making any profits in lockdown and the state of emergency.

Namibia depends on its natural resources and this includes tourism, which employs many semi-skilled and unskilled labourers. With borders closed and traveling banned to and from all countries around the world, the Namibian tourism industry was brought down to its knees and came to a standstill. The situation transformed many peoples' livelihoods as many lost their jobs, while some received reduced salaries. These changes affected people, and many could no longer afford their previous lifestyles; some couldn't fulfil their basic human needs like food.

COVID-19 is, indeed, calling for the need for increased organisational resilience and community well-being by embracing virtual collaboration tools and practices where possible. The future of work is no longer a model but a reality for Namibian organisations. Hence, sectors that have always been in the bloodshot were also the ones that were hit the hardest, such as construction and informal business—street vendors, local entrepreneurs, and other small and medium enterprises—as these sectors had no safety cushioning to deal with the reality of the pandemic. These sectors had no provisions for leave allocation, salary payment for employees working from home, monitoring of employees at home, travel restrictions and additional precautionary measures for such catastrophic events.

COVID-19 not only exposed the vulnerability of the tourism and health sectors but also that of local town and city authorities. Many Namibians in informal settlements do not have excess to running water and proper sanitation. The houses they live in are not of good quality. Housing has been a problem for the past years in Namibia and governments have not been very involved in the discussion around the land or house allocation. The Minister of Finance, honourable Iipumbu Shiimi, issued the first phase of the economic stimulus and N\$8.1 billion relief package to address the negative economic and social effects stemming from Namibia's first 21-day lockdown period. Under this scheme, each person received N\$750. This payment was meant for all unemployed Namibians, small and medium enterprise entrepreneurs, and all affected employees.

COVID-19: Culture and Interaction

COVID-19 has left a permanent mark on the world. It has changed the way

people interact with each other. An effective way to slow the transmission of the disease is by limiting physical interactions, such as handshaking and hugging as well as reduced traveling and work from home. This method is being used across the world to flatten the transmission curve. All this has led to fewer social interactions between people in society. In different communities in Namibia, more traditional responses to the pandemic and its ensuing isolation and lockdown measures have been seen and influenced by cultural preferences. Since staying at home at all times was never a part of many Namibian cultures, it forced many to disrupt the lockdown regulations. Furthermore, many people have no understanding of hand hygiene such as sanitising, washing hands regularly, and avoiding touching one's face. Ideally, the government policies could have used cultural beliefs and values as tools to contain the spread of the outbreak. The acquisition of new cultural and relative knowledge in containing the outbreak would have been a good technique to develop strategies and communication to educate and ensure understanding of the pandemic and its basics.

Research Methods

This research paper has adopted an exploratory qualitative approach, using ground theory as there is not much research done on COVID-19 in Namibia. According to Noble and Mitchell (2016), grounded theory is a research method that focuses on the generation of theory, which is "grounded" in data that has been systematically collected and analysed. It is used to uncover social processes such as social relationships, connections, experiences and behaviours of groups. Qualitative research was intended to lead the researchers to a better understanding of concepts, content and perceptions. Furthermore, qualitative approaches helped the researchers avoid simplifying collective experiences and rather explore the range of behaviours and perceptions as documented, expanding the understanding of the result through interviews (Corbetta, 2003).

The qualitative research adopted a thematic content analysis. Content analysis was used to generate themes and concepts on social and economic challenges in times of climate change and the COVID-19 pandemic. The method is normally used to systematically evaluate the symbolic contents of all forms of documentation (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Meanwhile, the empirical material analysis allowed the researchers to draw a description and classify various communications.

Findings and Discussion

Climate Change and COVID-19 on Social Crises: Poverty and Urbanisation

Literature proved that the COVID-19 pandemic and climate change in Namibia presented and created destruction on economies, social function,

global political and public health concerning the already existing social crises in society, such as inequality, poverty, urbanisation and gender-based violence. Social systems are often exposed to serious processes in which their institutions are questioned by society for solutions. Various social crises are interlinked to each other and determine changes and transformations in social, political and economic systems. This means that climate change does not exist as a single problem in society but is and will be impacted by other social crises, such as poverty or urbanisation. At first sight, they seem to be unrelated, but they form part of the same process that demand solution from society. Poverty in Namibia is linked to unemployment, and unemployment is linked to many other social evils in society. It may affect many parts of an individual's life—financial, social, psychological, environmental and political, as all these make up an individual's life cycle.

As mentioned earlier, the lockdown that was brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic forced people to work from home; thereby, increasing the time spent by people at home. Yet, Namibia reported a countrywide decrease in gender-based violence. Wolf (2020) reported that the police had recorded a total of 1,050 gender-based violence cases since January. This included assault, rape, robbery and murder typically involving alcohol abuse, which may be assumed as the root of the cause. Other police reports also seem to have decreased, while counselling organisations like ChildLine/LifeLine Namibia reported an increase from 10 to 36 domestic violence cases per month for March and April. Wolf (2020) clarifies that despite the lowering of reported police cases, they were actually on the rise. This is because most victims were forced to spend most of the lockdown with the perpetrators of abuse in urban areas. They could not leave. This was evident after the lockdown when the number of cases reported an increase country-wide. COVID-19 allowed society to be able to identify the need for change, especially regarding women's abuse. Many people are keen to go to the streets in protest, demanding that the Namibian government take cases of gender-based violence seriously and protect vulnerable groups of society. In this way, COVID-19 offered somewhat clear determinants and directives for a better understanding of social issues and their relative causes.

Climate change has had an impact on social systems too, with agriculture in rural Namibia having less production and loss of domestic animals as a result of drought. This has increased the rural community's dependency on urban areas for survival. Furthermore, governments have been unable to reduce absolute poverty levels or the very high inequalities in income distribution, which have only increased with time. Rural populations were most affected by extreme weather events in the past and continue to be identified as those most likely to be at risk from such events in the future. In the northwest part of Namibia, the great Kunene region, one could grasp the impact that drought

had on the Ovahimba community, an indigenous community with heavy dependence on agriculture for many years. The community is one of the few remaining tribes that have maintained their traditional lifestyle of pastoral and semi-nomadic livelihood. The Ovahimba community was one of the communities most impacted by the drought of 2011– 2019, as most of their cattle died. They had to develop new lifestyles in villages or migrate to urban areas to seek better living conditions. Many identified the urban lifestyle as much more accommodating than the village as they could perform small tasks for other people in return for money. They were involved in activities such as cleaning houses, laundry and raking yards.

To adapt to harsh climatic conditions and new health risks, society has transformed social functions and lifestyles. The increasing impact of climate change and COVID-19 has severely affected communities and continues to do so.

Climate Change and Local Economy Revitalisation During the COVID-19 Pandemic

It is important to note that COVID-19 and climate change are not as immoral as they appear. History and human evolution have taught us that the merging of several unrelated incidences has resulted in a change in human society, natural environment and shifting economic system. According to Gowdy (2019), unprecedented climate instability and the evolution of human society have allowed natural selection to operate on different populations, driven by the economic requirements of extra food production. Human society was transformed into an incorporated, interdependent and highly complex economic machine, which needs not only to produce for itself but others as well. The movement of people and animal products has increased from national travel and trade to global travel and trade. This has allowed the spread of diseases between animals and humans.

Climate change and COVID-19 have shown the need for society to transform and adapt to changes, as the pandemic exposed the vulnerability of public health in most developing countries and the economy at large. By analysing the Namibian economy, it is clear that there is a high dependency syndrome on neighbouring countries, especially South Africa. Most food and clothing products are imported as is expertise in certain domains. For all this, Namibia is dependent on South Africa. With the lockdown and ban on travelling, many Namibian retailers were forced to reckon with empty shelves as the products they needed were not in the warehouses. Since Namibia uses a road network through Botswana, it became a bigger problem as Botswana also wanted to close its borders to Namibian truck drivers. These roadblocks make it evident that Namibia needs more climate-resilient products that will sustain the environment and create a more independent economic system.

In addition to the challenges indicated, it is important for the Namibian government to create a more climate-resilient and health-adaptive economy. It is circumstantial at this point that there are no separate entities as health, education and the economy are interdependent. As part of economic revitalisation, the government should strengthen the agenda on the local economy by creating a supportive environment for local enterprises. This can be done by taking the following steps:

- Promoting manufacturing and productive activities by local entrepreneurs
- Ensuring that small and medium enterprises are empowered to grow through support and an enabling environment
- Allowing policies to be responsive to economic uncertainties would help mitigate further economic challenges, should another crisis arise
- Increasing the promotion of locally produced products to help entrepreneurs ensure that their products are bought to the market.
- Prompting indigenous knowledge to produce climate-resilient products, as most of the products produced by indigenous people are environmentally friendly (biodegradable) and sustainable
- Focusing on infrastructure development by providing infrastructures and services that are well linked to economic prosperity, such as bettering health services nationwide, ensuring running water for each homestead and providing each Namibian with an appropriate house and much-needed essentials.

Conclusion

COVID-19 silenced Namibia's tourism and hospitality industry. It made healthcare systems fear for their capacity and individuals fear for their job and income. On the other hand, climate change enables Namibia to pay closer attention to the interconnectedness of tourism and the global economy and modifies our attitudes towards tourism and the environment. Addressing the source causes of vulnerability to climate change and COVID-19 is a challenge not many governments are willing and ready to face. Henceforth, not all sections of the Namibian economy and society have been equally vulnerable to the impacts of climate change and COVID-19. In Namibia, industries such as telecommunication, digital markets, and online and distance education have not been much impacted by the pandemic as the operation of many organisations embraced to transform to this mode of communication and interaction. COVID-19 also created opportunities for some. For example, work from home and online teaching led to the use of technology and its supporting kits, which include devices, data bundles and network connections, to mention a few.

Climate change and COVID-19 allowed Namibia to witness how local governments, communities and other social actors can work in collaboration or independently to improve the health sector, infrastructure development and community engagement in the country. Now, a better understanding of the linkages between climate change, COVID-19 and the economy needs to be made to support decisions and pursue the enhancement of environmental benefits while ensuring sustainable products, health sector improvement and resilient economic development in a peaceful Namibia.

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